

Why Novels (Don't) Break Through: Dynamics of Canonicity in the Danish Modern Breakthrough (1870–1900)

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1 Introduction & Related Work

The process by which literary works gain canonical status often reflects a complex interplay of textual, socio-economic, and institutional factors (Brottrager et al. 2021). Who decides what constitutes ‘literary value’ and how do material factors influence the place of certain books in the canon? These questions remain central to ongoing debates about canon, which has unfolded across various literary cultures in recent years, including the Danish.

Recent quantitative studies of canonical literature have foregrounded the textual characteristics of canonical works, suggesting that the label does not exclusively arise from circumstantial factors (i.e., extra-textual features). Compared to non-canonical works, canonical works have been shown to have a unique textual profile (Barré et al. 2023; Brottrager et al. 2021; Porter 2018), with stylistic characteristics connected to a higher cognitive load on the reader (Bizzoni et al. 2024; Wu 2023; Wu et al. 2024). These recent findings are revealing, especially since the canon debate has focused on the arbitrariness and circumstance of the canon label, ascribed, at large, to the influence of extra-textual features (Guillory 1995; von Hallberg 1983).

Our recent study (Feldkamp et al. 2024) – as well as recent work by Barré 2024 – distinguishes itself from these earlier studies by relying on representations of novels in semantic space, that is, going beyond the stylistic perspective through which canonicity is often examined. We explored characteristics of Danish novels from the Modern Breakthrough era (1870-1900) to examine whether canonical works distinguish themselves through innovation and impact. Similar to other recent findings in the French literary field (1600-1950), our findings affirmed the distinction of canonical novels in terms of innovation and impact (Barré 2024). Still, we also found a category of novels with similar textual profiles to canonical novels that, however, remain less known today. This suggests that factors beyond textual qualities – such as the spread of novels, their accessibility to readers, and the socio-economic conditions surrounding their production – may play a significant role in determining canonicity.

In this paper, we continue on that by investigating broader socio-economic and institutional contexts of literary production, focusing on text-extrinsic factors – specifically, book prices, publishing houses, and the author’s nationality – as predictors for a novel’s canonicity. We test the strength of text-extrinsic features for determining the canonical status of a novel in a classification task. We compare this to the performance of exclu-

sively text-intrinsic features as used in (Feldkamp et al. 2024), as well as the combination of text-extrinsic features and text-intrinsic features.

We use an exhaustive corpus of novels from a specific period in Danish literature, namely the Modern Breakthrough (1870–1900) – in Danish, *det Moderne Gennembrud*. This was a transformative period in Danish literature, marking a shift from romanticism to realism and naturalism. Spearheaded by critic Georg Brandes,¹ the movement emphasized literature’s capacity to reflect and critique society, focusing on social issues, individualism, religion, and scientific inquiry (D’Amico 2016; Bjerring-Hansen and Wilkens 2023). The period saw an unprecedented rise in literary production and readership, with the novel emerging as the dominant genre, with connected changes in pricing and publishing dynamics, i.e., the rise and fall of certain publishers.

The polarization between realist and popular literature (specifically, the historical novel) underscores the evolving dynamics of literary authority, literary market, and audience reception in this period, making the Modern Breakthrough a compelling case for examining which text-extrinsic factors contribute to a novel’s canonicity. While realist novels gained prestige and a place in the literary canon, popular genres like the historical novel declined, even as demand for accessible literature rose (Bjerring-Hansen and Wilkens 2023). These dynamics suggest that factors beyond textual qualities – such as dissemination, readership demographics, and the socio-economic conditions of literary production – played a significant role in forming canonicity. By focusing on how literary innovation, societal reflection, and external forces interacted during this period, the Modern Breakthrough provides valuable insights into the mechanisms that shape literary canons (Bjerring-Hansen and Wilkens 2023; Watt 2001; Armstrong 1987).

2 Corpus

Our dataset comprises 838 original Danish and Norwegian novels published between 1870 and 1900, accompanied by metadata such as page count, book prices, and publishing houses. Notably, all novels, including those by Norwegian authors, were published in Danish and by Danish publishers. The corpus includes all first-edition novels from Danish publishers during this period, excluding non-novel works like short story collections.²

We use our earlier created categorization of novels’ canonical status (Feldkamp et al. 2024). Our list of the canon included authors indexed in the Educational Canon (*Undervisningskanon*) and the Cultural Canon (*Kulturkanon*), introduced by the Danish government in the early 21st century to promote Danish literature and standardize school curricula (Harbild et al. 2004). However, the government-defined canons exclude Norwegian authors and are likely driven by political agendas. To provide a more expert-driven perspective, we collected a canon list from the encyclopedia *Den Store Danske*,

¹Brandes’ first Copenhagen lecture of the series “Hovedstrømninger” (1871), and the publication of J.P. Jacobsen’s *Mogens* (1872) are often pinpointed as the start of the Modern Breakthrough (Bjerring-Hansen and Rasmussen 2023).

²This compilation, known as the MiMe-MeMo corpus, was developed by Jens Bjerring-Hansen, Philip Diderichsen, Dorte Haltrup, and Nanna Emilie Dam Jørgensen, based on the Danish book index (Dansk Bogfortegnelse). Version 1.1, utilized in this study, is accessible at: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/MiMe-MeMo/Corpus-v1.1>.

specifically its entry on ‘det moderne gennembruds litteratur.’³ Novels featured in the Cultural Canon, written by authors mentioned in the Educational Canon, or listed in the entry of ‘det moderne gennembruds litteratur’ in *Den Store Danske* are labeled as *Canon*, while all others are categorized as *Other*. (See corpus statistics and category details in Table 1.⁴)

	<i>titles</i>	<i>authors</i>
Corpus	838	361
Canon	114	20
Other	724	342

Table 1: Statistics on the corpus.

3 Methods

We approach the central question of this paper as a classification task. Based on intra-textual and extra-textual features of a novel, can we predict its canonicity? We take the following approach:⁵

1. Creating document representations. To build a compact representation of the texts, we use the `m-e5-large-instruct` model to create a semantic embedding of each novel.⁶ Each novel is divided into chunks of the same size,⁷ and embeddings were created for every chunk. The average embedding of all chunks of a novel is then used as a representative embedding for that novel.

2. Selection of text-extrinsic features. For each novel, we collect its first edition price, the editor that published it, and the nationality of the author, to represent some aspects of the novels’ text-extrinsic profile.

3. Preparing classification tasks. We perform a classification task using a simple Random Forest model. Random Forest was chosen for this task because it shows robust performance with mixed data types (continuous and categorical) and, through its ensembling, effectively mitigates overfitting. It is also a robust model, well suited for handling outliers. The two classes we are working with are *Canon* and *Other*.

4. Sampling. Because our two classes are unbalanced, we randomly downsample the larger class (*Other*). In order to guarantee robustness, we repeat the majority class downsampling (and training/testing) 50 times and take the average precision, recall, and

³See https://denstoredanske.lex.dk/det_moderne_gennembruds_litteratur.

⁴An extended dataset with additional tags is available on <https://huggingface.co/datasets/chcaa/memo-canonical-novels>.

⁵To ensure reproducibility, code and raw data are available at https://github.com/centre-for-humanities-computing/dhb_danish_canon/.

⁶See <https://huggingface.co/intfloat/multilingual-e5-large-instruct>. This model was the best performing in an earlier task that included the historical Danish MeMo-BERT model Al-Laith et al. 2024, the best-performing Danish sentence encoder DFM-large (Enevoldsen et al. 2023), and the two best-performing open-weight models on SEB, `m-e5-large` and its prompt based version `m-e5-large-instruct` (Wang et al. 2024). See (Feldkamp et al. 2024).

⁷Since the maximum chunk size includes the length of the prompt, we use a chunk size of $512 - 87 = 425$ characters.

	Canon		Other	
	<i>titles</i>	<i>authors</i>	<i>titles</i>	<i>authors</i>
Danish	68%	70%	86%	89%
Norwegian	32%	30%	13%	10%
German	0%	0%	1%	1%

Table 2: Distribution of author nationalities within the corpus, based on number of authors and novels.

Figure 1: Book prices across categories within the corpus.

F1-score across all 50 runs as our results. In each run, we reserve 10% of the data for testing.

5. Experiments. To model the impact of text-intrinsic and text-extrinsic features on the process of canonization, we experiment with the following features: (1) text-intrinsic features, i.e., embeddings, and (2) text-extrinsic features, i.e., price, publisher, and nationality. We run experiments with all possible combinations of these four features. The average sentence length is used as baseline feature.

6. False positives analysis. To detect non-canonical novels that contain a textual profile similar to canonical novels, we closely analyse the false positives from the experiments that result from running the model only on text-intrinsic features, i.e., embeddings.

4 Results

The results we will discuss in our presentation, will be divided in three sections: (1) Descriptive statistics, (2) Classification tasks, and (3) Not breaking through.

4.1 Descriptive statistics

We find that both the distribution of publishing houses and original book price vary between categories. Table 4.1 shows that, on average, prices of canonical books are higher than those of non-canonical books. The heatmap in Figure 2 shows that almost all canonical books are published by six of the largest publishing houses. Together, they are responsible for 94% (107) of all canonical novels. However, there are other large publishing houses where no canonical novels were published, and smaller publishing

Publisher	CANON	OTHER Category	TOTAL	Publisher	CANON	OTHER Category	TOTAL
Gyldendal	52	162	214	Henriques & Bonfils	0	1	1
Reitzel	13	49	62	Harald Kjellerups	0	1	1
Schubothé	17	38	55	Hans Jensens Forlag	0	1	1
Det Nordiske Forlag	10	36	46	Gravenhorfts Forlag	0	1	1
Schou	5	35	40	Emil Bergmann	0	1	1
Jydsk Forlags-forretning	0	27	27	Colberg	0	1	1
Philipsen	10	17	27	Chr. Steen & Søn	0	1	1
A. Behrend	0	26	26	E. Jespersen (Otto Schwartz)	0	1	1
V. Pio	0	16	16	E. E. Lohses	0	1	1
Schønberg	0	15	15	Digmann Silkebjerg	0	1	1
Jordán	0	12	12	Dansk Alnoldsblad	0	1	1
Hast	0	11	11	Emil F. Petersen	0	1	1
Chr. Steen & Søn	0	10	10	Folketidendes Bogtrykkeri	0	1	1
J. L. Wulff	0	10	10	F. Sørensen	0	1	1
Hagerup	0	9	9	A. C. Riemenschneiders Forlag	0	1	1
Gad	1	8	9	Behrendts Enke	0	1	1
Rom	0	9	9	Andersen	1	0	1
Carl Lund	0	9	9	Adelgade 9	0	1	1
Hagerup	0	8	8	Afholdsboghandel	0	1	1
Jens Møller	0	8	8	Borchorst	0	1	1
P. Olsen	0	7	7	Bønnelycke	0	1	1
Erslev	1	6	7	Björn Bjarnasons Forlag	0	1	1
Cammermeyer	0	6	6	Bielefeldt	0	1	1
Gjellerup	0	6	6	C. W. Stincks	0	1	1
Salmønsen	3	6	6	C. Rasmussens Forlagsboghandel	0	1	1
Mansa	0	6	6	C.G. Birch	0	1	1
H.C. Andersen	0	5	5	C. Würtz	0	1	1
N.P. Hansen	0	5	5	Carl Jensen	0	1	1
Axel Andersen	0	5	5	Ch. Michaëlsens	0	1	1
A. Andersen	0	5	5	Chr. Kragelund Jensen	0	1	1
Mackeprang	1	4	5	Chr. Mackeprangs Forlag	0	1	1
Eibe	0	4	4	A. Jacobsen	0	1	1
E. Meyers	0	4	4	N. M. Kjærs Forlag	0	1	1
Bergmann	0	4	4	Morso Folkeblad	0	1	1
Milo	0	4	4	N. B. Koussgaard	0	1	1
Jacob Lunds Forlag	0	4	4	Mad. Jørgensen	0	1	1
Th. Ørfeldt	0	4	4	Madsen-Lind	0	1	1
R. Andersen	0	4	4	Lohmannske Forlagsforretning	0	1	1
S. Trier	0	3	3	M. A. Schultz	0	1	1
W. Janssen	0	3	3	L. Petersen	0	1	1
Prior	0	3	3	L.A. Jørgensen	0	1	1
R. Stjernholm's forlag	0	3	3	Lind	0	1	1
Alex Brandt	0	3	3	Lehm & Stage	0	1	1
Simonsen & Co.	0	3	3	Iversens	0	1	1
Wroblewsky	0	3	3	J.H. Brinck	0	1	1
Joh. Møller	0	3	3	Jydsk Forlags-Forretning	0	1	1
A. Christiansen	0	3	3	K. Christensen	0	1	1
A. Christiansen	0	3	3	J. L. Wisbech	0	1	1
Forfatteren	0	3	3	J. C. Jensen	0	1	1
K. Jørgensen	0	2	2	J.C. Koch	0	1	1
K. Foren. f. i. M.	0	2	2	Magnus Hansens Eft.	0	1	1
Jespersen	0	2	2	N. Pedersen	0	1	1
Nyt Forlagsbureau	0	2	2	S. Birck	0	1	1
Kihl & Langkjaer	0	2	2	Pastor Holt	0	1	1
Forfatteren	0	2	2	Philipsen	0	1	1
Frimodt	0	2	2	S. Brodersen	0	1	1
Ernst Bojesen	0	2	2	Strandberg	0	1	1
B. Diederichsen	0	2	2	Th. Gandrup	0	1	1
C. Pedersens Boghandel	0	2	2	Thaaning & Appel	0	1	1
A. W. Henningsen	0	2	2	V. Pontoppidan	0	1	1
H.C. Jacobsen	0	2	2	V. Nielsen	0	1	1
Nørrejdsk Forlag	0	2	2	Z. Richter	0	1	1
Horstmann	0	1	1	Zeuner	0	1	1

Figure 2: Number of novels in each category published by a given publishing house. Note that overall, the *Other* category generally has a higher entropy in its distribution over publisher than the *Canon* category. Entropy, $Other = 3.66$, $Canon = 1.72$. This difference persists when downsampling the majority group.

houses with a more even canon/non-canon ratio. Furthermore, these statistics show that publishing houses that are responsible for a large part of the canon production, also publish non-canonical books. Table 2 contains the distribution of author nationalities within our corpus, including both the distribution of unique authors and the distribution of all novels.

4.2 Classification tasks

The average performances of the classification experiments are summarized in Table 3. In nearly all experiments, the baseline performance based on average sentence length is surpassed. Embeddings alone appear to be strong predictors for canonicity, yielding F1-scores of 0.728 for the *Canon* class and 0.677 for the *Other* class.

However, several text-extrinsic features or combinations thereof also obtain a high performance when predicting canonicity in our corpus. The average F1-scores range between 0.389 and 0.753. This reveals that text-extrinsic features also serve as good predictors for a novel’s inclusion in the canon. When text-extrinsic features are combined with embeddings, F1-scores for the *Canon* class fall within the range of 0.718 to 0.739, suggesting that together they achieve a similar performance in predicting canonicity.

To evaluate whether these results are disproportionately influenced by the very long tail of smaller publishing houses – each publishing only one novel – we conduct the same classification experiments on a subset of the corpus. This subset includes novels from the eight publishing houses that each contribute to the dataset with more than 25 novels (see Figure 2). The performance metrics for these experiments are shown in Table 4.

4.3 Not breaking through

In our presentation, we will discuss Figure 3 and 4 in more detail.

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Figure 3: Ratio of true negatives (TN) and false positives (FP) of non-canonical novels that are incorrectly classified as canonical based on *embeddings*, when using other feature sets. We only include novels of which 75% of the predictions for *embeddings* are FP . The unique number of novels is 145. Every novel is predicted 12 times.

Figure 4: Heatmap of false positives (FP): non-canonical novels incorrectly classified as canonical based on *embeddings* as features. Columns represent feature sets, with cell values showing normalized false positive counts ($FP/(TN + FP)$). We only include novels of which 75% of the predictions for *embeddings* are FP ($embeddings \geq 0.75$). The unique number of novels is 145, and every novel is predicted 12 times.

Type	Feature set	Precision		Recall		F1-score	
		Canon	Other	Canon	Other	Canon	Other
Baseline	avg_sentence_length	0.511	0.514	0.828	0.213	0.585	0.222
Text-extrinsic	price	0.551	0.553	0.560	0.534	0.545	0.534
	publisher	0.647	0.864	0.909	0.501	0.753	0.620
	nationality	0.633	0.549	0.293	0.839	0.389	0.662
	price_publisher	0.648	0.676	0.683	0.622	0.658	0.638
	price_nationality	0.580	0.580	0.551	0.601	0.554	0.581
	publisher_nationality	0.647	0.857	0.905	0.505	0.752	0.624
	price_publisher_nationality	0.657	0.684	0.691	0.637	0.667	0.652
Text-intrinsic	embeddings	0.681	0.764	0.795	0.624	0.728	0.677
Combination	embeddings_price	0.685	0.754	0.780	0.639	0.723	0.683
	embeddings_publisher	0.684	0.738	0.772	0.627	0.718	0.667
	embeddings_nationality	0.693	0.764	0.790	0.642	0.731	0.686
	embeddings_price_publisher	0.694	0.775	0.804	0.641	0.739	0.692
	embeddings_price_nationality	0.688	0.756	0.782	0.642	0.726	0.685
	embeddings_publisher_nationality	0.691	0.756	0.783	0.643	0.728	0.686
	embeddings_price_publisher_nationality	0.690	0.749	0.778	0.643	0.726	0.684

Table 3: Performance of Random Forest models based on a baseline (avg. sentence length) and different feature sets: text-extrinsic features only, text-intrinsic feature (embeddings), and a combination of text-extrinsic and -intrinsic features. The dataset is down-sampled to have balanced classes (114 data points per class). Values represent average results across 50 iterations. In **green**: the best settings for that class. In **bold**: the best predicted class for those settings.

Type	Feature set	Precision		Recall		F1-score	
		Canon	Other	Canon	Other	Canon	Other
Baseline	avg_sentence_length	0.512	0.667	0.936	0.142	0.656	0.200
Text-extrinsic	price	0.536	0.544	0.516	0.564	0.518	0.546
	publisher	0.540	0.622	0.729	0.376	0.599	0.428
	nationality	0.627	0.537	0.302	0.807	0.393	0.642
	price_publisher	0.571	0.605	0.638	0.516	0.596	0.543
	price_nationality	0.559	0.547	0.540	0.564	0.538	0.546
	publisher_nationality	0.573	0.571	0.576	0.556	0.562	0.549
	price_publisher_nationality	0.573	0.588	0.618	0.527	0.585	0.542
Text-intrinsic	embeddings	0.719	0.738	0.724	0.709	0.713	0.713
Combination	embeddings_price	0.698	0.715	0.709	0.685	0.695	0.691
	embeddings_publisher	0.692	0.706	0.711	0.671	0.694	0.681
	embeddings_nationality	0.722	0.726	0.720	0.711	0.713	0.712
	embeddings_price_publisher	0.701	0.714	0.715	0.684	0.700	0.691
	embeddings_price_nationality	0.703	0.730	0.735	0.676	0.710	0.692
	embeddings_publisher_nationality	0.705	0.715	0.716	0.685	0.703	0.692
	embeddings_price_publisher_nationality	0.698	0.737	0.747	0.667	0.714	0.692

Table 4: Performance of Random Forest models based on a baseline (avg. sentence length) and different feature sets: text-extrinsic features only, intra-textual feature (embeddings), and a combination of extra- and intra-textual features. **The dataset only includes the novels of large publishing houses of which we have more than 25 novels in our dataset.** We have down-sampled to have balanced classes (107 data points per class). Numbers represent average results across 50 iterations. In **green**: the best settings for that class. In **bold**: the best predicted class for those settings.

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